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Research Article

**COMPARISON OF THE OUTCOMES OF PREGNANCY
AMONG MULTIPAROUS AND PRIMIPAROUS FEMALES
PRESENT WITH INCREASING AGE****Aqsa Rahat, Zara Amjad, Wania Ashfaq**
Faisalabad Medical University Faisalabad**Article Received:** February 2020**Accepted:** March 2020**Published:** April 2020**Abstract:****Objective:** To compare the outcomes of pregnancy in multiparous and primiparous females below and over 35 year of age.**Methodology:** This research work is a comparative study which recruited 1021 females having pregnancy and the comparison of the outcomes of pregnancy carried out in four groups of multiparous and primiparous females below and over 35 year of age. SPSS V.20 was in use for the statistical analysis of the collected information.**Results:** There was a strong association between age over 35 years and pre-eclampsia, Gestational Diabetes Mellitus, Cesarean Section, preterm labor, and low weight at the time of birth in primiparous females. In multiparous females, there was a strong association between age of less than 35 year of age, low weight at the time of birth and pre-eclampsia. Among females over 35 year of age, parity is effectual on measure of delivery through cesarean and pre-eclampsia.**Conclusion:** Increased maternal age can be an important factor for the outcomes of pregnancy. There is more affection of age on the primiparous females. Aged females can get normal delivery through vagina with term baby.**KEY WORDS:** Gestational Diabetes Mellitus, Preterm, Cesarean, Primiparous, pre-eclampsia, Pregnancy.**Corresponding author:****Aqsa Rahat,**
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INTRODUCTION:

Increasing age of the mothers is very important risk factor for the outcome of pregnancy [1]. Increase age of the females have strong impact on the process of pregnancy and labor [2]. In current time, females delay their pregnancies up to 4th and 5th decades of their lives due to various reasons as qualification and occupational reasons or delay in marriages [3]. Majority of the female's experience pregnancy against their will and due to failed contraception, almost 10.0% pregnancies normally occur at over 35 years of age [4]. According to a research report, the mean age of first marriage has been increased to 4.70 years from 1974 to 1998 and because of this, there is an increase in the mean age of maiden pregnancy [5]. Some research works are available with the claim that midwifery incidents and prenatal mortality are augmented in females with over 35 years of age [6]. The outcome of the research work conducted by Yusuf stated that among primiparous females with over 35 years of age, the rate of Cesarean Section is 2 times higher than multiparous female with above 35 years of age [7].

Camille has stated the association between the augmented rates of risk of prenatal mortality and low eight at time of birth. He described the increased age as an important risk factor associated with prenatal death [8]. Pasupathy Diamentra found that rate of prenatal death is 2 times higher among aged females at the time of delivery [9]. This research work carried out with the rationale to compare the outcomes of pregnancy in multiparous and primiparous females over 35 and below 35 years of age.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This research work is a descriptive study. Ethical committee of the Hospital gave the permission to conduct this research work. We completed the volume of samples in every group. We filled the

registration card which contained the information about outcome of pregnancy as Cesarean Section, Gestational Diabetes Mellitus, preterm labor, placenta prevail, pre-eclampsia, and low weight at the time of birth. We entered all this gathered information in SPSS V.20 for statistical analysis. We compared the measured outcomes in groups of primiparous females with over 35 years of age with primiparous females below 35 years of age, multiparous females with over 35 years of age with multifarious females below 35 years of age as well as primiparous females with over 35 years of age with the multiparous females having 35 years of age. All the patients suffering from other serious complications as genital infections, having less than twenty years of age, females with habit of cigarette smoking, addicted females or suffering from other heart or kidney diseases were excluded from this research work. The estimation of the needed samples carried out in each group with certainty measure of 45.0% and evaluation power of 80.0%. Finally, the estimation of needed samples set as one thousand people.

RESULTS:

According to data of medical files, there were 250 primiparous females over 35 years of age, 254 primiparous below 35 years of age, 257 multiparous females over 35 years of age and 255 multiparous females under 35 years of age. Age group of 20 to 24 years of age had highest number in group of primiparous females below 35 years and the mean age of these females was 24.020 ± 3.385 years. Age group from 25 to 29 years of age was present with highest number of multiparous females below 35 years of age and the mean age of these patients was 26.710 ± 3.761 years. Age group from 35 to 39 years of age had highest number of multiparous females over 35 years and mean age of these females was 36.810 ± 2.319 years.

Group Pregnancy Outcome	Primiparous		Multiparous		Odds-Ratio (95%CI)	P-Value	X ²
	35>		20-34				
	No	%	No	%			
Preeclampsia	52	20.8	15	5.8	2.335, (7.817-4.272), CI%95	25.69	<0.001
Gestational diabetes	16	6.4	7	2.7	0.995, (6.090-2.462), CI%95	4.031	0.045
Placenta prevail	4	1.6	1	0.4	37.795, (4.195- 0.466), CI%95	*	0.209
Preterm labor	53	21.2	36	13.9	1.047, (2.652-1.677), CI%95	4.699	0.03
Mal presentation	20	8	7	2.8	1.206, (6.997-2.905), CI%95	6.135	2.905
Cesarean	161	64.4	123	47.5	2.000, (2.855-2.855), CI%95	14.74	<0.0001
Low birth weight	58	23.2	30	11.6	1.426, (3.729-2.306), CI%95	12.005	<0.0001

Approximately 28.20% multiparous females were under 35 years of age, regardless of the increase of Cesarean Section in aged multiparous females, X² test stated that this increase was much significant statistically. Low weight at birth in primiparous females above 35 years was 23.20% versus 11.60% in primiparous below 35 years of age. χ^2 test stated a significant association between low weight at birth and age over 35 years among primiparous females (P= 0.0010) and OR measure displayed that pregnancy in over 35 years of age would rise the danger of low weight at birth about 2.305 times. approximately 16.80% multiparous females over 35 years would have low weight at birth, although this number is 9.0% in multiparous females over 35 years. X² test found that there would be a significant association between maternal over age and low weight at birth in multiparous females (P= 0.0090). Primiparous labor augments the rate of occurrence of pre-eclampsia 2.227 times and Cesarean Section as 3.771 times higher among aged females. High age of mother can be an important risk factor for the outcome of pregnancy.

Group	Primiparous		Multiparous		P-Value	Odds-Ratio (95! CI)	X ²
	No	Percent	No	Percent			
Pregnancy Outcome							
Preeclampsia	52	20.8	27	10.5	0.001	2.218(1.342,3.665)	10.092
Gestational diabetes	16	6.4	13	5.1	0.522	1.273(0.599,2.704)	0.409
Placenta prevail	4	1.6	5	2	1	0.813(0.217,3.076)	*
Preterm labor	53	21.2	44	17.2	0.252	1.290(0.827,2.012)	1.314
Malpresentation	20	8	13	5.1	0.189	0.536(0.211,1.367)	1.729
Cesarean	161	64.4	83	32.4	<0.0001	3.771(2.609,5.448)	51.802
Low birth weight	58	23.2	43	16.8	0.072	1.489(0.959,2.313)	3.246

Fisher test *

DISCUSSION:

The findings of this research work showed that 20.80% primiparous females with over 35 years of age had pre-eclampsia whereas this rate was 5.80% among females under 35 years of age. X2 test displayed that there is strong relation between age over 35 years and presence of pre-eclampsia among primiparous females. Jacobson has stated that there was an increase in the occurrence of severe preeclampsia with the increase in age but there was a decrease in the mild pre-eclampsia [10]. There is no acknowledged cause for this contradiction. Shiner has stated that 6.40% primiparous females over 35 years of age, suffering from gestational diabetes mellitus, although this amount is 2.70 among primiparous females with under 35 years of age [11]. The results of this research work stated that in primiparous females over 35 years of age, 1.60% females were present with placenta Previa, where the rate of this complication is 0.40% for females below 35 years.

In this research work, Fisher test stated that there is no association between age of the females over 35 years and placenta Previa among primiparous females. This similar finding is also outcome of one other research work. Michael has stated that there is no strong association between the measures of Placenta Previa and over age of females [12]. The results of this research work stated that the measure of placenta previa among multiparous females above 35 years of age was 20.0% but this rate was nil among multiparous females with below 35 years of age. The results of this current research work state 17.20% multiparous females with over 35 years have had preterm labors since this measure was 9.0% among multiparous females under 35 years of age. χ^2 test stated that there was a strong association between age over 35 years and preterm labor. OR volume showed pregnancy in age of below 35, enhances the danger of preterm labor for 2.1030 times. Temmerman also stated the strong association between increasing age of mothers and preterm labor.

This current research work have displayed that rate of occurrence of mal-presentation among primiparous females over 35 years in 8.0% versus 2.80% in females below 35 years, 5.10% multiparous females over 35 years of age were present with mal-presentation which was 2.70% in females below 35 years.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of this research work showed that pregnancy would enhance the danger of Cesarean Section in primiparous females over 35 years of age. The matter of fact is that aged females can have normal delivery through vagina with term baby and

over age females must not be contraindication for the pregnancy.

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